

Isolation of Mesenchymal Cells and their Relationship with Blood Vessels Formation at Early Stages of Gestation in the Human Fetus

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Abstract

Objective: The aim of this study was to compare the areas occupied by mesenchymal cells and the areas of blood vessels for the same stage of gestation. In the same way, the lengths and widths of the mesenchymal cells grouped around the vascularization and the same isolated cells were measured and compared. Materials and method: Tissue of the temporal region of 10 aborted human fetuses at 12 weeks of gestation was removed in 10 cubic millimeter blocks. The blocks were embedded in paraffin, and these paraffin-embedded blocks were sectioned serially in sagittal planes 6 μm wide with a rotatory microtome. Hematoxylin-eosin staining was used in each of the histological sections for detect or not the presence of mesenchymal cells and vascularization respectively. The area occupied by blood vessels and mesenchymal cells was measured and compared with the use of image j software. The student's T-test was used to compare the areas occupied by mesenchymal cells and the areas of vascularization. Similarly, the same statistical test was used to compare the lengths and width between cells that occupied colonies or were isolated. Conclusion: mesenchymal cells occupied a larger area than blood vessels zones. The width of the isolated cells was considerably larger. However, the comparison of cell lengths between isolated cells and those occupying colonies did not show marked differences. The isolated cells were observed close to areas of osteoid tissue.

Keywords: Stem Cells; Stromal Cells; vascularization zones; Human fetus

Introduction

Non-hematopoietic mesenchymal cells have a high capacity for differentiation into multiple cell lineages. These types of cells tend to be located at the perivascular level, and among their important properties is the formation of bone and cartilage tissue. They have been placed in almost all tissues, but especially at the perivascular level [1]

There has been a lot of interest in studying stem cells and there are clear reports on the isolation of mesenchymal cells. Similarly, studies have been carried out in vitro cultures to observe their proliferation and differentiation. Mesenchymal stem cells have been described as multipotent cells with a high capacity for differentiation and self-renewal that circulate in fetal blood. They have been isolated at different stages of early development. However, the fetal stage has special characteristics because it is the only period in which there is a migration in large numbers of stem cells [2] and [3]

It has been mentioned that the chorionic villi of the placenta are rich in stem cells and these cells that are located in niches have an active

function in the repair of tissues of the human placenta, in the differentiation of other cells such as adipocytes, chondrocytes, and osteocytes. Blood vessel niches host a group of mesenchymal cells that will play an important role in histodifferentiation [4]

The role of blood vessels in the construction of tissues derived from various cellular sources, including various types of stem cells, has been extensively investigated. Additionally, this type of cell has a variety of functions in terms of tissue vascularization processes, both through its direct contact and through indirect signaling mechanisms [5]. In addition to molecular signals, there are several important factors in promoting vascularization and among them are precisely interactions with various cell populations.

There are interdependent roles between mesenchymal cells and vascularization in the formation of new functional tissues. Paracrine and endocrine signals influence the behavior of stem cells. But, mechanical stimuli can have an impact on vascularization. During pregnancy, the placenta plays a vital role in endocrine

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function. For this reason, a failure in these functions leads to intrauterine growth retardation [6]. In addition to paracrine and endocrine effects that impinge on vascularization, stem cells may have a direct effect on blood vessel formation through direct endothelial differentiation [7].

The processes of angiogenesis are mediators in the activation of endothelial cells, and in the same way, through a process of increased vascular permeability, they ensure blood flow [8]

Mesenchymal cells have been associated as promoters of angiogenesis [9]. In the same way, blood vessels provide oxygen and nutrients to all cells, and the disposition of this oxygen acts as a regulatory mechanism. The research question is: in the early stages of gestation is there an interrelationship between mesenchymal cells and the neo-vascularization process? The aim of this study was to compare the areas occupied by mesenchymal cells and the areas of blood vessels formation for the same stage of gestation. In the same way, the lengths and widths of the mesenchymal cells grouped around the vascularization and the same isolated cells were measured and compared.

Materials and methods

Histological sections

Tissue of the temporal region of 10 aborted human fetuses at 12 weeks of gestation was removed in 10 cubic millimeter blocks. These selected areas are close to the formation of chondrogenesis processes or osteoid tissue (fig 3) formations that have been previously evaluated. These blocks were fixed in 10% stabilized neutral formalin containing 40% formaldehyde, 4.0 g of sodium dehydrogenate phosphate, and 6.5 g of disodium hydrogen phosphate at Ph 7.0 and stored at 4°C. The blocks were embedded in paraffin, and these paraffin-embedded blocks were sectioned serially in sagittal planes 6 µm wide with a rotatory microtome. Fifteen sections were obtained for each temporal area. Sections were deparaffinized and hydrated in distilled water.

Procedure for washing histological sections

Histological sections were placed in each slide and numbered. All previously numbered cuts were washed with PBS 0.2 M (pH 7.2) by 45 minutes with 15-minute intervals to complete 3 washes with PBS. All histological sections were kept at room temperature and without

contact with light. Hematoxylin-eosin staining was used in each of the histological sections for detect or not the presence of mesenchymal stromal cells and vascularization respectively.

Histological evaluation

Evaluation Criteria

Type I: absence of mesenchymal cells around vascularization.

Type II: presence of mesenchymal cells isolated from vascularization

Type III: Formation of mesenchymal cell colonies surrounding blood vessels formation

Exclusion Criteria

All those histological sections that were defective or that did not allow a clear view of the area under study were discarded

The selected sections were photographed and digitalized. A quantitative analysis was performed for each serial group of histological sections of the study area. The total amount of cells present in the temporal zone of each histological section was counted and measured the area occupied by these cells.

Mesenchymal cell counting and measurement

Cell counting was performed by optical field considering the presence of isolated cells or cells grouped in colonies around blood vessels. Mesenchymal cells were measured in length and width. These measurements of isolated cells were compared with cells that formed colonies.

Morphometric analysis.

All the images were obtained through a transmitted light microscope (Kyowa Medilux-12) with video camera (motic 2000) and motic images 2.0 Multilanguage, the same Graduated object holder with metric scale standard and 400 x magnifications were used in all histological sections. Application software for the acquisition of the differences in staining properties and morphology facilitating identification of all studied.

Analysis of the area occupied by blood vessels and mesenchymal cells

The area occupied by blood vessels and mesenchymal cells was measured and compared with the use of image j software, each photomicrographs were taken with the same objective of the microscope and using in all the samples one bar of 30 -micron scale, the same resolution, the same optical configuration and the same size of image.

Statistical procedure

The student's T-test was used to compare the areas occupied by mesenchymal cells and the areas of vascularization. Similarly, the same

statistical test was used to compare the lengths and width between cells that occupied colonies or were isolated.

No fetus used in this study had any visible evidence of developmental abnormalities or genetic disorders. To carry out this study, samples of aborted human fetuses were used in accordance with procedures approved by the department of the physiology of the Medicine School of the University of Los Andes. All the conditions of Helsinki declaration related to research in diseased human subjects were observed.

Results

Only 10% were classified as type II because mesenchymal cells were isolated from blood vessels (fig 1). In 90% of the histological sections evaluated, a homogeneous distribution of mesenchymal cells was observed, forming colonies around the blood vessels.

Fig 1- It is possible to observe an isolated mesenchymal cell and its diameter is larger than the cells occupying colonies.

All the results of the histological sections obtained from the temporal region of the 10 fetuses studied that met the inclusion criteria were observed and analyzed, allowing the following results: Type I = 0, Type II = 1 and Type III = 9. In the comparison between the areas occupied by vascularization processes and colonies of mesenchymal cells (Tables 1, 2 and 3), it was possible to observe a greater area occupied by mesenchymal cell niches than the areas occupied by blood vessels (graph 1 and figure 2)

Table 1

Comparison between the area of mesenchymal cells and the area of vascularization

Area of mesenchymal cells	Área of vascularization
1047093	740214
1015094	735984
1045854	443902
1254651	788712
821040	376608
1056084	452070
1275056	725920
1034453	720525
1234561	432175

Table 1 shows comparisons of the areas occupied by clustered mesenchymal cells in relation to the area of vascularization.

Table 2
Descriptive Statistics of the Areas

Variable	Minimal	Maximum	mean	Desv. Standard
Area of mesenchymal cells	821040.000	1275056.000	1087098.444	144980.094
Área of vascularization	376608.000	788712.000	601790.000	168980.844

The table shows the descriptive statistics of the means of the areas occupied by mesenchymal cells and the area of vascularization

Table 3 - Comparison of statistical means

	485308.
Diferencia t (Valor observado)	444
t (Valor crítico)	8.440
GL	2.306
valor-p (bilateral)	8
alfa	<
	0.0001
	0.05

Interpretation of the test

H0: The difference between the means is equal to 0.

Alternative hypothesis: (Ha) The difference between the means is different from 0.

Since the computed p-value is less than the significance level $\alpha=0.05$, the null hypothesis H0 should be rejected, and the alternative hypothesis accepted.

Graph 1

Comparison between the means of the areas of mesenchymal cells and the area of vascularization

The graph shows the difference between the means of the areas occupied by mesenchymal cells and the area of vascularization

By comparing the widths of clustered and isolated cells, it was possible to observe that isolated cells are considerably wider than clustered cells (tables 4, 5, 6 and fig 2). This evidence between the cell widths can also be observed in the graph 2.

Table 4
Comparison between Width of Isolated Cells and Width of cells in colonies

Width of Isolated Cells	Width of cells in colonies
86	63
111	57
96	50
89	37
90	47
87	45
102	39
94	55
90	49
60	60

Fig 2-It is possible to observe the relationship between the vascularization areas and the mesenchymal cells that surround it.

The table shows the comparison between the measurements of the width of both cell groups, the cells in colonies and the cells in isolates

Table 5
Descriptive statistics of the comparison between the widths of the cells studied

Width of Isolated Cells	10	60.000	111.000	90.500	13.168
Width of cells in colonies	10	37.000	63.000	50.200	8.613

Statistical table showing the difference in cell width values in colonies and isolates

Table 6
Comparison of Means of Cell Widths

Difference	40.300
t (Observed Value)	7.215
t (Critical Value)	2.262
GL	9
P-value (two-sided)	< 0.0001
alpha	0.05

Interpretation of the test:

H0: The difference between the means is equal to 0.

Ha: The difference between the means is different from 0. Since the computed p-value is less than the significance level alpha=0.05, the null hypothesis H0 should be rejected, and the alternative hypothesis

(Ha) should be accepted.

Graph 2- Comparison of means of widths

The graph shows the difference between the mean widths of both types of cells studied.

During the comparison of both clustered and isolated cell groups, no marked differences were observed in the length of the two cell groups studied (tables 7, 8, 9 and graph 3)

Table 7

Comparison of lengths between isolated and clustered mesenchymal cells

Length of cells in colonies	Length of isolated cells
217	256
215	288
266	291
278	239
240	242
257	260
260	278
273	227
280	234
286	280

Table 7 shows comparisons of the lengths of the mesenchymal cells studied. It can be seen that no major differences were found between them

Table 8

Descriptive Statistics of the Comparison of Lengths between Isolated and Clustered Mesenchymal Cells

Variable	Obs. No data lost	Minimal	Maximum	Means	Desv. typical
Length of cells in colonies	10	215.000	286.000	257.200	25.407
Length of isolated cells	10	227.000	291.000	259.500	23.600

Table 8 shows the descriptive statistics of the comparisons of the lengths of the mesenchymal cells studied.

Table 9- Comparison of Mean Lengths between Isolated and Clustered Mesenchymal Cells

Difference	-2.300
t (Observed Value)	-0.187
t (Critical Value)	2.262
GL	9
P-value (two-sided)	0.855
alpha	0.05

Interpretation of the test:

H₀: The difference between the means is equal to 0. H_a: The difference between the means is different from 0. Since the calculated p-value is greater than the significance level $\alpha=0.05$, the null hypothesis H₀ cannot be rejected.

Mesenchymal cells close to the processes of osteoid tissue formation were observed (fig 3). Clustered mesenchymal cells were observed between zones of formation of new blood vessels, and in the same way isolated cells were observed in greater numbers towards areas of osteoid tissue formation (fig 4)

Fig 3- It is possible to observe mesenchymal cells (red arrow) very close to the formation of osteoid tissue (black arrow) and vessel

formation (yellow arrow).

Fig 4- Areas of clustered cells (green arrow), isolated mesenchymal cells (black arrows), and zone of vascularization (yellow arrow)

colonies did not show marked differences. The isolated cells were observed close to areas of osteoid tissue.

Discussion

The main findings of this study are to observe the intimate relationship that mesenchymal cells have with vascularization processes in these stages of gestation. In the same way, it is possible to observe that in these stages of human development these cells are related to histodifferentiation as well as the formation of osteoid tissue. Although the vast majority of histological sections showed clusters of cells around vascularization, other cells were found isolated and close to the processes of osteoid tissue formation. These cells had a wider shape than the clustered ones. Differentiation of mesenchymal stem cells to osteoblasts, are stimulated by proteins, responsible for bone induction. These proteins are part of a group known as growth factors [10]. These cells can differentiate in vitro into a wide variety of cells, including osteoblasts, chondrocytes, and adipocytes. In the same way, they can proliferate in culture, have clinical applications, and be implanted in the same patient [11]. It has been reported that bone ossification begins with fetal life and continues through ontogeny through bone remodeling [12]; [13]. In the events of direct and indirect ossification, osteoblast differentiation is stimulated, and angiogenesis plays an important role in bone formation. For this reason, it is possible to understand the relationship between vascularization processes and the presence of mesenchymal cells that surround the new vessels in these stages of gestation.

Conflict of interest: The author declares that he/she has no conflict of interest with any person or institution regarding this research.

Ethical aspects: all ethical aspects according to the Helsinki norms were observed. Immediately after the samples were taken, the fetuses were returned to the hospital.

Conclusion: mesenchymal cells occupied a larger area than vascularization zones. The width of the isolated cells was considerably larger. However, the comparison of cell lengths between isolated cells and those occupying

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